

Position Location of Failed Fuel in PWR-Core during Operation based on Fine Nuclide Composition Simulation

Songzhe Wang, Yunzhao Li*, Yuancheng Zhou, Yisong Li, Yilin Liang

Xi'an Jiaotong University, 28 West Xianning Road, Xi'an, Shaanxi 710049, China

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20803654

ABSTRACT

Fuel rod failure in Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) poses a serious safety risk due to the possible release of radioactive nuclides into the primary loop. Existing techniques mainly rely on the concentration and variation of a few fission product nuclides in the primary loop. They can accurately identify fuel failure and determine the breach size during core operation, but fail to locate the position of failed fuel in the core. This study proposes a novel, precise, and universal failed fuel location technology leveraging detailed nuclide composition information. Firstly, by using the reactor core physics analysis software NECP-Bamboo, the detailed physics-burnup process can be simulated to obtain the fine nuclide composition evolution of each fuel rod based on its detailed specific operating history. Secondly, a fission product diffusion and release model can be employed to calculate the dynamic release of nuclides into the primary circuit upon any supposed fuel failure. Thirdly, a failed fuel feature database can be constructed if each of the fuel rod in the core can be assumed to be failed. Fourth, a deep metric learning network is then used to probabilistically match the measured nuclide activity concentration in the primary circuit with this database, pinpointing the most likely failed fuel location. In this study, preliminary results using the BEAVRS benchmark show high discrimination. The detailed nuclide calculation revealed significant differences in the primary circuit nuclide feature vectors for different fuel assemblies, even those of the same type with varying operating histories. It verifies the theoretical feasibility and great potential of this method, which overcomes the limitations of traditional techniques and offers a new pathway for online, precise location without requiring reactor shutdown. Future work will focus on integrating and verifying this technology with actual nuclear power plant operating and measurement data to facilitate its engineering application.

Keywords: Fuel Rod failure, Location Technology, NECP-Bamboo, Damage Feature Database

1. INTRODUCTION

Fuel rod failure is almost an unavoidable phenomenon during the operation of pressurized water reactors (PWRs). According to statistics from the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) on discharged fuel assemblies from global PWRs between 2006 and 2015, the average number of broken fuel rods in each damaged fuel assembly of a pressurized water reactor is 1.3 [1]. Once the fuel rod cladding fails (e.g., due to hydrogen embrittlement, debris fretting, grid-to-rod fretting, or excessive oxidation[2]), radioactive fission products from the fuel pellet will leak and enter into the reactor's primary coolant, leading to a significant increase in primary loop activity concentration, posing a serious threat to public safety and plant operation. Therefore, the diagnosis and localization of fuel failure are important. On one hand, it is necessary to determine the size and number of failures without reactor shutdown during operation for safety risk assessment. This in-operation diagnosis is vital to avoid premature or unplanned reactor shutdowns, which entail significant economic losses and operational disruptions. On the other hand, accurate localization helps to adjust the fuel management plan in advance, reduce the additional impact caused by the failed assembly, and efficiently locate and process the failed fuel assembly during the subsequent outage.

*Email address: yunzhao@mail.xjtu.edu.cn.

In the field of fuel failure localization technology, various methods have been developed domestically and internationally. For instance, CEA's DIADEME [3] and EDF's MERLIN [4] from France primarily rely on the analysis of the release rate of inert gases (such as Xe) and iodine isotopes in the primary coolant; Russia's RTOP-CA [5] uses an adaptive neural network algorithm for diagnosis; and Westinghouse's FPA/CADE[6] combines Xe-133 and four iodine nuclide activities, utilizing the Cs-137/Cs-134 ratio to estimate the burnup range. Additionally, the China Nuclear Power Institute [7] and CGN [8] have also proposed their respective failure diagnostic criteria.

However, traditional methods generally suffer from three major limitations: First, their fission product source term calculations mostly adopt simplified burnup models (considering only a dozen nuclides), ignoring the nuclide composition differences caused by operating history; Second, the number of isotopes used for judgment is too few (mainly focusing on Xe and I); Third, they rely heavily on extensive historical operating data to form judgment criteria, which leads to strong limitations for specific reactor types and an inability to directly locate the possible failed assembly position. To overcome these challenges, this study proposes a precise fuel failure location technology based on detailed nuclide composition information and a deep metric learning network. By considering the fuel's operating history, this research utilizes self-developed core physics analysis software (NECP-Bamboo and Bamboo-SFuel) to conduct sophisticated physics-burnup coupling calculations, accurately simulating the nuclide composition of every single fuel rod. Building upon this, a damage characteristic database containing multiple measurable nuclides is constructed, and a deep metric learning network is applied to probabilistically match the measured primary loop activity with the database, thereby achieving high-precision localization of the failure position. This method overcomes the strong dependence of traditional techniques on historical operating data, offering a new approach for achieving online, universal, and precise diagnosis of fuel failure in nuclear power plants.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Technical Scheme

The failed fuel rod localization technology proposed in this paper mainly consists of three critical steps: the precise calculation of nuclide composition before failure, the creation of the damage feature database, and the determination of the failure location. The overall computational flowchart is shown in *Figure 1*.

Figure 1. Computational flowchart.

First, NECP-Bamboo [9] is utilized for full-life power tracking calculations. Subsequently, Bamboo-SFuel performs precise nuclide composition calculations at the single fuel rod scale. Next, a fission product diffusion and release model are integrated to simulate the nuclide release into the primary circuit upon break, and to construct the damage feature database containing multiple measurable nuclides. Finally, a deep metric learning network is used to probabilistically match the measured nuclide activity concentration data in the primary circuit with the database, thereby achieving high-precision localization of the failure location.

2.2. Precise Calculation of Nuclide Composition in the fuel

The exact, history-dependent nuclide composition for every single fuel rod can be achieved through the integrated NECP-Bamboo and Bamboo-SFuel [10]. NECP-Bamboo performs core operation tracking calculations, recording the detailed three-dimensional power and burnup history. These data are input into Bamboo-SFuel, which conducts detailed nuclide composition and fission product source term calculations, considering a comprehensive set of nuclides. Bamboo-SFuel refines the spatial mesh division down to the single fuel rod level using the modular characteristic method. This tightly coupled process outputs the precise instantaneous nuclide composition for every rod at any operating time. This detailed nuclide source term then serves as the foundation for the failure release simulation, which accounts for the primary release mechanisms: knock-out, recoil, and diffusion.

2.3. Precise Calculation of Nuclide Composition in the primary loop

After obtaining the detailed nuclide source term for the fuel rod, this paper integrates the fission product release model and the primary loop kinetics equations to simulate the complete process of nuclide dynamic release from the failed fuel rod into the primary circuit and its subsequent migration in the coolant. When the fuel cladding develops a defect, fission product release undergoes an initial transient stage of enhanced release due to pressure pulsation, followed by a steady state dominated by the diffusion transport mechanism. The following two-stage kinetics equations are used to describe the change in nuclides as they are released from the cladding gap into the primary circuit and within the primary circuit[11], as shown in Equation (1) and Equation (2):

$$\frac{dN_{G,i}}{dt} = \nu_i N_{P,i} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \gamma_{ij} \lambda_j N_{G,j} - (\lambda_i + \varepsilon_i + \sigma_i \phi) N_{G,i}. \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dN_{C,i}}{dt} = \varepsilon_i N_{G,i} + \sum_{j=1}^{i-1} \gamma_{ij} \lambda_j N_{C,j} - \left(\lambda_i + \frac{Q}{W} \eta_i + \beta + \tau \sigma_i \phi + \frac{L}{W} \right) N_{C,i}. \quad (2)$$

where, $N_{G,i}$ is the number of fission product i's atoms in gap; $N_{P,i}$ is the number of atoms in pellet; $N_{C,i}$ is the number of atoms in coolant; $N_{G,j}$ is the number of fission product j's atoms in gap; ν_i is release rate of pellet to gap, s^{-1} ; γ_{ij} is the proportion of the decay of nuclide j into nuclide i, λ is the decay constant, s^{-1} ; ε_i is release rate of gap to coolant, s^{-1} ; W is total coolant mass, t; Q is primary loop coolant flow rate reduction, $t \cdot s^{-1}$; L is primary loop coolant leakage rate, $t \cdot s^{-1}$; η_i is purification efficiency; β is primary loop boron purification rate, ppm/s; τ is proportion of the primary loop coolant remaining in the reactor core.

2.4. Creation of Damage Feature Database

By solving the aforementioned kinetics equations, this study can accurately calculate the steady-state activity concentration of various measurable nuclides in the primary loop coolant following the failure of any single fuel rod in the core. Based on this, the damage nuclide database containing the unique characteristic vector for each fuel rod can be constructed as the direct basis for diagnosis using the deep metric learning network.

2.5. Training of a Neuro Network to Inverse the Failing Probability Distribution

After that, the high-dimensional nuclide activity data calculated for each potentially damaged fuel rod from the damage nuclide database, representing a unique "nuclide fingerprint" for every core location. To distinguish these vectors effectively, a Deep Metric Learning (DML) model based on an Encoder structure is designed (as shown in [错误!未找到引用源。](#)). The Encoder maps the input characteristic vector into a low-dimensional, discriminative embedded space. Model training uses a self-supervised learning paradigm and a weighted cross-entropy loss function, compelling the network to learn the unique features of each position by maximizing the similarity of a vector to itself and minimizing it against all others in the batch.

For diagnosis, the measured primary loop activity data is embedded by the trained model, and its similarity to all database vectors is calculated. These similarities are then converted into a probability distribution via the Softmax function, yielding the matching probability for each historical failure position, thereby achieving precise localization. This method utilizes detailed nuclide information and the powerful feature extraction capabilities of deep learning, breaking the dependence of traditional methods on historical data of specific reactor types, and providing a breakthrough theoretical basis for achieving online, universal, and precise diagnosis of fuel failure.

Figure 2. Neural network flowchart of Failure Location Determination.

3. PRELIMINARY RESEARCH RESULTS

To verify the feasibility of the fuel cladding failure localization technology based on detailed nuclide composition information proposed in this paper, a series of preliminary research works were conducted, simulating and verifying multiple steps from nuclide calculation and failure location determination.

3.1. Detailed Nuclide Composition Calculation for the BEAVRS Core

First, we used the self-developed core physics analysis software NECP-Bamboo to perform full-cycle tracking simulation calculations for the internationally recognized BEAVRS benchmark[12]. The calculation results showed that key parameters such as the critical boron concentration, control rod worth, and power distribution were in good agreement with the reference values, indicating that the calculation model could accurately reproduce the actual operating history of the core, providing a reliable foundation for subsequent nuclide composition calculations. Based on this precise modeling, the Bamboo-SFuel was further utilized to perform detailed calculations of the nuclide composition of every single fuel rod in the core at different burnup times. Bamboo-SFuel can consider the detailed irradiation history and perform fine radial and axial meshing of fuel assemblies, thereby obtaining comprehensive nuclides, including actinides, fission products, and activation products, providing a rich data basis for failure localization. The results of the BEAVRS cycle 1 calculation are shown in *Figure 3*. The numbers in *Figure 3(a)* indicate the number of the burnable poison rods. The results shown above

are at EOL and a total of 1547 nuclides were calculated.

Figure 3. Calculation of nuclide composition in BEAVRS core.

3.2. Direct Distinguishability Verification of Nuclide Composition at Radial Quarter-Core Scale

To assess the ability of nuclide composition to distinguish the failure location, a concept verification calculation was performed. Assuming a failure occurred in an assembly in the core center region, the established calculation chain was used to simulate the stable concentration of nuclides formed in the primary loop coolant after the failure of all assemblies in the radial quarter-core. The activity values of over 40 representative nuclides (including Am, Cs, I, Kr, Xe, etc.) were selected to form the characteristic vector. Similarity was assessed by directly calculating the Euclidean distance between the characteristic vectors of each assembly; a smaller distance indicates more similar nuclide characteristics.

The preliminary results in Figure 4 show significant differences in nuclide characteristics between different types of fuel assemblies, as reflected by the larger Euclidean distance values. This suggests that the method, which relies on detailed nuclide composition, has the potential to overcome a key limitation of traditional methods, which can typically determine the number of failures but struggle to locate them. However, for assemblies of the same type, the distinguishability based on direct Euclidean distance calculation remains relatively low. This indicates the need for more advanced algorithms to extract deeper features for precise localization.

3.3. Deepening Research on Localization Capability at Eighth-Core Scale

To further investigate the method's ability to distinguish assemblies of the same type, the research scope was narrowed to an eighth-core, focusing on Type A fuel assemblies, whose enrichment is 1.6%. Assuming a failure occurred in the 19th axial layer of assembly A020, the primary loop nuclide characteristic vector upon failure of each Type A assembly was calculated. Similarly, the vector distance was calculated to assess similarity. The results showed that although the assembly types were the same, due to their specific position in the core and differences in their micro-operating history, their nuclide characteristics still possessed a certain degree of distinguishability, but the distinguishability was limited and needed enhancement through pattern recognition algorithms. The detailed distance calculation results are shown in [错误!未找到引用源。](#)

Figure 4. Direct distinguishability verification of nuclide composition at radial quarter-core.

Figure 5. Localization capability at eighth-core scale.

3.4. Failure Probability Calculation based on Deep Metric Learning

To address the shortcomings of the direct comparison method, a deep metric learning network was introduced. Focusing on Type A assemblies, we assumed a failure occurred in the 5th axial layer of assembly A008 and generated the corresponding damage nuclide database as the training and testing set. First, under ideal conditions (without considering measurement uncertainty), the neural network demonstrated extremely high localization resolution. The failure probability distribution map calculated by the network showed that the probability value of the failure location (A008-05) was significantly higher than all other locations, enabling precise localization. The probability distribution under ideal conditions is shown in Figure 6(a).

Figure 6. Failure probability calculation based on deep metric learning.

Subsequently, a measurement uncertainty of 30% was introduced to simulate a more realistic engineering environment. Under this condition, although the calculated failure probability of the failure location (A008-05) was not necessarily the maximum value, its probability value was still significantly higher compared to the vast majority of non-failed locations, showing clear distinguishability. The probability distribution after introducing uncertainty is shown in *Figure 6 (b)*.

This result fully proves the robustness of the method proposed in this paper. Even in the presence of significant measurement errors, this technology can still effectively narrow down the suspicious failure range, providing strong decision support for subsequent detailed inspection, and possessing significant engineering application value.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of this study clearly indicate that the fuel cladding failure localization technology based on fine nuclide composition information is highly feasible and has significant advantages at the theoretical level. Through comprehensive simulation calculations on the BEAVRS core, we systematically verified the breakthrough nature, discriminability, and robustness of this technology compared to traditional methods.

First, the precise nuclide calculation reveals the inherent "nuclide fingerprint" differences among various fuel assemblies, which serves as the physical basis for failure localization. However, for assemblies of the same type, the localization ability achieved through direct vector distance comparison alone is limited, which highlights the necessity of introducing the Deep Metric Learning (DML) network to extract subtle, non-linear features.

The introduction of the DML network greatly enhances localization accuracy and methodological robustness. Under ideal conditions, the neural network demonstrated nearly perfect localization resolution. More importantly, the method exhibits good robustness when faced with unavoidable measurement uncertainty in real-world engineering. Even with the introduction of 30% measurement uncertainty, the calculated probability value of the damaged assembly remains significantly higher than the vast majority of non-failed locations. This result has important engineering significance, indicating that the technology is a practical decision support tool capable of significantly narrowing

down the suspicious range, thus avoiding the "needle-in-a-haystack" fault detection process, saving both time and economic costs.

The advantage of this technology lies in its "forward calculation" logic, which predicts nuclide characteristics by precisely simulating the physical process, thereby reducing the reliance on specific reactor historical failure data and providing stronger universality.

Naturally, this study still has limitations. The current model idealizes the primary loop system parameters; future work must focus on deep coupling and verification with actual plant operating data, and further expansion of the database to cover a wider range of operating conditions and failure types.

In summary, the results and discussion presented herein fully validate the correctness of the proposed technical route, proving the fundamental feasibility of using fine nuclide composition for failure localization, and demonstrating the immense potential of this method to move from a theoretical model to engineering application by introducing intelligent algorithms and considering engineering uncertainties.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No.12575186).

REFERENCES

- [1] IAEA *Review of fuel failures in water cooled reactors (2006-2015): An Update of IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NF-T-2.1*. Vienna: IAEA, 2019: 10-11. URL <https://www.iaea.org/publications/8259/review-of-fuel-failures-in-water-cooled-reactors>.
- [2] K.-T. Kim, "Relation between a fuel rod failure cause and a reactor coolant radioactivity variation," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 248, pp. 156–168, Jul. 2012, doi: [10.1016/j.nucengdes.2012.03.051](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2012.03.051).
- [3] D. Parrat, J.B. Genin, Y. Musante, et al. "Failed rod diagnosis and primary circuit contamination level determination thanks to the Diademe code," *Fuel failure in water reactors: Causes and mitigation*, Bratislava, Slovakia, 17–21 June 2002.
- [4] B. J. Lewis, P. K. Chan, A. El-Jaby, F. C. Iglesias, and A. Fitchett, "Fission product release modelling for application of fuel-failure monitoring and detection - An overview," *Journal of Nuclear Materials*, vol. 489, pp. 64–83, Jun. 2017, doi: [10.1016/j.jnucmat.2017.03.037](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2017.03.037).
- [5] V. Likhanskii, I. Evdokimov, A. Sorokin, V. Kanukova, A. Khromov, and E. Afanasieva, "Failed fuel diagnosis during WWER reactor operation using the RTOP-CA code".
- [6] D.L. Burman, O.A. Correal, H.W. Wilson, et al. "Development of a coolant activity evaluation model and related application experience", *American Nuclear Society*, Avignon, France (1991), p. 363
- [7] Jing Futing, Lyu Huanwen, Tang Songqian, et al. "Research on Fuel Rod Damage Diagnosis Method Based on Big Data." *Nuclear Power Engineering*, Vol. 45, pp. 150–155, 2024, doi: [10.13832/j.jnpe.2024.S2.0150](https://doi.org/10.13832/j.jnpe.2024.S2.0150)
- [8] Tang Shaohua, Lyu Weifeng, Xiong Jun, et al. "Development of Calculation Code CFPF for Fission Product in Primary Loop of Pressurized Water Reactor Nuclear Power Plant." *Nuclear Power Engineering*, Vol. 39, pp. 33–38, 2018, doi: [10.13832/j.jnpe.2018.04.0033](https://doi.org/10.13832/j.jnpe.2018.04.0033)
- [9] Y. Li et al., "Development and verification of PWR-core fuel management calculation code system NECP-Bamboo: Part I Bamboo-Lattice," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 335, pp. 432–440, Aug. 2018, doi: [10.1016/j.nucengdes.2018.05.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2018.05.030)
- [10] Y. Li et al., "Bamboo-SFuel: A nuclide composition evaluation code for PWR spent fuel in NECP-Bamboo," *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, vol. 438, p. 114047, Jul. 2025, doi: [10.1016/j.nucengdes.2025.114047](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucengdes.2025.114047)
- [11] B. Dong, W. Xiao, J. Yin, and D. Wang, "Detection of fuel failure in pressurized water reactor with artificial neural network," *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, vol. 140, p. 107104, Jun. 2020, doi: [10.1016/j.anucene.2019.107104](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anucene.2019.107104).
- [12] N. Horelik, B. Herman, B. Forget, and K. Smith. Benchmark for Evaluation and Validation of Reactor Simulations (BEAVRS), v1.0.1. *Proc. Int. Conf. Mathematics and Computational Methods Applied to Nuc. Sci. & Eng.*, 2013. Sun Valley, Idaho